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Remedy for Account Hacking, Login Credentials of all sectors after not using Accounts and Person's Death

*Corresponding

Author:- Jitendra Sunte
Assistant Professor,
Department of
Mechanical Engineering,
Lingaraj Appa
Engineering College,
Bidar, Karnataka, India

*Jitendra Sunte**

*Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical
Engineering, Lingaraj Appa Engineering College, Bidar,
Karnataka, India*

ABSTRACT

In day-to-day life man has opened so many accounts in the social sector, financial sector, technical sector, medical sector, and education sector, like Facebook accounts, email IDs, WhatsApp, IPR IDs, WIPO IDs, ChatGPT, Amazon IDs, Flipkart IDs, bank accounts, share marketing accounts (Upstox, Motilal Oswal), PhonePe, Paytm, and Google Pay. For all these, one needs to memorize login credentials. After a person's death, who is responsible for further processing or closing the account? These accounts are hacked and ruled a little bit by some people. In this paper one has to clear the concepts and who is responsible to take these challenges in a systematic manner to resolve these problems. In social media you might have observed messages like "My account has been hacked; don't respond to pay money." In this paper fake and dummy rulings are controlled by some actions; precautions should be taken to facilitate smooth running operations after closing accounts.

Keywords:-*Hacking, fake ruling, login credentials, Retrieve, closing accounts, Negative species*

1. INTRODUCTION

In day-to-day life persons and peoples are facing so many troubles if they do not have memories of login credentials, PINs, and passwords while signing up and signing in. In the Google Password Manager, the option is there if he wants to save the credentials, but these are not safe after not using the account for so many months. Retrieving and closing an account is a tedious process, and it is not so simple to close the account. Account opening is so simple, but account closing is very complicated in all the field processes. While immediately after a person's death, these accounts are utilized in a bad manner by someone, and the main victim is the key person who is handling a few operations for misutilization in a non-systematic manner, who is called a hacker.

2. NEGATIVE SPECIES BAD ROLE IN HACKING

In almost all economic and social fields like these, so many persons are uncontrolled in a way called single-sense-level sex, called non-independent manner. In this after-sense level sex, authorized staff or ministers' accounts are accessed, then an instant ruler or hacker plays unwanted rights, and finally, he cracks and withdraws money from other persons. Sense-level sex is the offense, and how many senses humans have is how many of those types of sex will happen. Suppose a person has hand-based sex, and then after does not agree to sign, but then also he makes the sign officially and loses the authorization and money. These are called bad pitrus and are hackers in almost all sectors. Other relevant staff in those particular fields know credentials, and these are called earth-level present-time hackers. These staff you can visualize, you can see. These thieves' staffs are punishable ones. But negative species, which came from the Nadir side, the adho disha side, and the lokas, are the main thieves to misuse the account, and finally

data sharing, transferring, and fraud will be arising in all sectors. The person when and where death has happened you can't say, but the closing of all his accounts was immediately made after the person's death.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

One needs to prevent single and multi-sense level unwanted sex of individuals. Also need to self-control and self-independent in all social and economic fields and all sectors in life. If n number of sex is there then n number of sex is present. A person can have seen to individuals after death if he has not do sex to anyone which is the biological way of camera which is best known the hypothesis of camera.

4. CONCLUSION

- In day-to-day life man has opened so many accounts in the social sector, financial sector, technical sector, medical sector, and education sector, like Facebook accounts, email IDs, WhatsApp, IPR IDs, WIPO IDs, ChatGPT, Amazon IDs, Flipkart IDs, bank accounts, share marketing accounts (Upstox, Motilal Oswal), PhonePe, Paytm, and Google Pay. For all these, one needs to memorize login credentials
- In social media you might have observed messages like "My account has been hacked; don't respond to pay money." In this paper fake and dummy rulings are controlled by some actions; precautions should be taken to facilitate smooth running operations after closing accounts.
- In day-to-day life persons and peoples are facing so many troubles if they do not have memories of login credentials, PINs, and passwords while signing up and signing in. In the Google Password Manager, the option is there if he wants to save the credentials, but these are not safe after

not using the account for so many months.

- But negative species, which came from the Nadir side, the adho disha side, and the lokas, are the main thieves to misuse the account, and finally data sharing, transferring, and fraud will be arising in all sectors. The person when and where death has happened you can't say, but the closing of all his accounts was immediately made after the person's death.
- One need to prevent single and multi-sense level unwanted sex of individuals. Also need to self-control and self-independent in all social and economic fields and all sectors in life.
- If n number of sex is there then n number of sex is present. A person can't see to individuals after death if he has not do sex to anyone which is the biological way of camera which is best known the hypothesis of camera
- Prevention of sense level sex is the remedy for all accounts which should be safe in manner

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